

Open ModelE (OpenME)

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Scientific & Technical Management

The OpenME project goal is to release an open source version of the NASA Goddard Institute for Space Studies (GISS) ModelE global climate model (GCM). The NASA ModelE GCM is used to research past, present, and future climate including human-induced climate change. Results from ModelE and earlier versions of the code have been used in presentations before the U.S. Congress and in global assessments such as the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) reports (e.g., Hansen *et al.* 1983, Hansen *et al.* 2005, Schmidt *et al.* 2006, Hansen *et al.* 2007, Schmidt *et al.* 2014, Kelley *et al.* 2020, Miller *et al.* 2021, Nazarenko *et al.* 2022). ModelE development and use as a research tool is funded primarily by NASA. The White House Office of Science and Technology Policy (OSTP) has declared 2023 a “Year of Open Science”, and NASA has similar initiatives (e.g., NASA TOPS). Making the ModelE source code openly available to all scientists, researchers, and the public is therefore a key step to both White House and NASA goals of making research more transparent, accessible, inclusive, and reproducible.

Summary of Scientific Goals of Parent Proposal

The OpenME effort is applying for supplemental funding under NASA ROSES 2023 F.8 which requires an existing funded ‘parent’ proposal. The parent proposal (from NASA MAP) is titled “GISS ModelE Development FY20-FY24” which was focused on enhancing the functionality and ease of use of the GISS ModelE to facilitate applications for the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 6 (CMIP6) and onwards. Additionally, ModelE is the basis for multiple other grants from the Modeling, Analysis and Prediction (MAP), Atmospheric Composition Modeling and Analysis Program (ACMAP), Interdisciplinary Research in Earth Science (IDS), Living with a Star, and Planetary Science programs. This includes efforts to improve the modelling of the factors affecting regional sea level rise (SLR) and improve the assessments of the risks of coastal flooding. The effort also includes higher resolution atmospheric runs (ModelE3) that can represent changes in tropical cyclones, and higher resolution ocean eddy-permitting simulations (ModelE4) used to refine estimates of climate change on ocean circulation, sub-ice shelf-ocean interactions and shifts in storm statistics. Other applications include modelling sun-climate interactions in support of the Heliophysics *Living with a Star* program, and development, support and application of ROCKE-3D, a ModelE branch with expanded functionality for modelling climates on any rocky planet or moon with an atmosphere or ocean (such as Mars, Venus, Titan, and Europa, or many exoplanets).

Open Science Activities and Community Benefit

Activities

In order to make ModelE properly available to the public, we need to modify the ModelE source code to remove proprietary algorithms currently used in the code. This task is described in detail below (see WP1 and WP2 in Fig. 1). We will also support end-user access by performing code cleanup and unifying documentation (WP3) and providing a containerized version of ModelE (WP4) so that it can be run on a wide variety of hardware. Finally, we will follow the NASA Software Release Process (WP5).

Replace Proprietary Algorithms: ModelE development has taken place over the past ~40 years and used a variety of coding styles from Fortran 66 through modern object-oriented Fortran 2018 standards and language features. During this time developers have used

functions provided by, among others, Numerical Recipes (Press *et al.* 1996). Numerical Recipe (hereafter NR) codes printed in the book are copyrighted and licensed commercially by the NR authors, and their use is restrictive and incompatible with open science best-practices. However, the NR copyright does not protect the ideas, only the particular implementation. If the same idea is expressed differently, even with identical functionality, the new program would no longer be bound by the NR licence. Several existing open source libraries aim to provide algorithms that are fully open. For example, the GNU Scientific Library (GSL) Design Document (Galassi *et al.* undated) lists the NR licence as a motivation for creating GSL. GSL is written in C, but functions in GSL that implement the same features as the functions we need to replace in ModelE can be translated to FORTRAN.

Test: We will implement several levels of testing and document the effect of the changes: Function-level offline testing will occur first. For this test, we will run ModelE as-is multiple times to capture natural random variability. We will capture the inputs to and outputs from the NR functions for a range of inputs and outputs from the multiple function calls per run and the multiple runs. We will then extract the NR functions to a stand-alone executable that can be run without the larger ModelE framework (input files, supporting scripts, etc.). We will then run the stand-alone executable against all the inputs and verify that, in stand-alone mode, we are able to recreate the outputs bit-for-bit. Next, we will pass the inputs to our replacement and verify the replacement outputs against the NR outputs. Finally, we will replace the NR function in the ModelE framework and do full ModelE runs using the replacement function. This begins the larger ModelE-level testing.

One of the key requirements for ModelE is bit-for-bit reproducibility, assuming the same configuration and code is run on the same hardware, compiled with the same compiler and compiler options, etc. The functions we have identified so far are on the order of ~100 lines each and have clearly defined mathematical properties. Ideally, replacing functions preserves bit-for-bit compatibility, and this will be tested. However, if bit-for-bit compatibility is not maintained, this is acceptable if results are still physically reasonable and small.

Cleanup & Document: ModelE is currently documented primarily within the code via code comments. The limited public documentation is not kept up-to-date with code changes. As part of this effort we will improve code documentation, remove stale (unused) code that is no longer used, and remove out-of-date non-code documentation. We will also set up a documentation system and template for future documents. Full documentation of a GCM is a significant effort that is out-of-scope of this proposal, but by removing old stale documentation, and building the infrastructure for improved future documentation, we aim to support future developers and better documentation processes in the future.

Containerize: Once the proprietary algorithms have been replaced, ModelE could then proceed through the NASA Software Release Process. However, in this state, ModelE may be legally “open” but it still relies on a variety of default assumptions about hardware, compilers, input files, etc. that do not support transparent, accessible, inclusive, and reproducible research. To support these important open science goals we will,

- Build and release a docker container with instructions on how to get running on any Docker-supported system, and on generic consumer-grade hardware (e.g. normal laptop)
- Document the ModelE configuration scripts for public use
- Release input files for a standard historical run and future projections. Files will be uploaded to Zenodo and given a DOI to support reproducibility. Zenodo supports both a top-level DOI for the latest version of a given data-set, but also provides unique DOIs each time any files are updated. Therefore, future papers using (and contributing) data from (to) Zenodo can efficiently provide a DOI to the specific versions of files used.

Release: After removing proprietary algorithms and containerizing, we will follow the NASA Software Release guidelines to release the software per NASA standards.

Benefits

The benefits of the above are primarily a more transparent and accessible code base. The downstream effects of transparency and accessibility are hard to quantify, but transparency should support reproducibility, and accessibility should increase inclusivity. Additionally, if an open source model supports an open development process, there may be benefits including increased contributions from non-GISS developers (e.g., Braga *et al.*, 2023), and personnel recruitment to GISS through increased visibility of the development process.

Development Plan

Code and environment development will be primarily by co-I Mankoff, with oversight and advice from PI Schmidt, and will use the existing development environment until the proprietary code has been removed. We will run ModelE on Discover, the NASA Center for Climate Simulation (NCCS) primary computing platform: an > 100,000-core supercomputing cluster and an assembly of multiple Linux scalable units built upon commodity components capable of nearly 8.1 petaflops. For short runs, which are all that is needed to test minor code changes that should not change outputs, personal computers provide sufficient hardware resources. As soon as ModelE meets the licensing requirements for public release (i.e., no NR algorithms) we will begin the NASA software release work package. Work will continue on both Discover and personal computers on the containerization and documentation effort. Once the model is allowed to be released to GitHub, work will continue there following open-science best-practices.

Fig 1. Gantt chart showing project timeline, work packages, and milestones.

Data Management and Open Science Updates to the Parent Award

This effort does not significantly change the parent award data management plan, except that once ModelE is available on GitHub, the nightly snapshot page may link there.

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